

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Report

Polish case study: Results of the survey on immigrants coming to CEE

Polish results of the survey on immigrants coming to CEE

Case Study

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable "*D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries*" of the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. The work on this topic was done within Work Package 6 in Task 6.2: "*Thematic study 2 – Migration in Central and Eastern European Countries – destination & origin region in the future - analysis of immigration and emigration patterns and integration of immigrants in EU CEE countries*".

The report presents results of a pioneering survey on immigrants in EU CEE countries, using the Polish and Małopolska region as a case study. The survey was conducted in the period of October-December 2021. The final sample consists of almost 600 observations.

Based on this data, we evaluate the socio-economic integration and adaptation processes of recent immigrants in Poland and investigate their future migration intentions and preparedness. The most striking finding is that most of immigrants declare to settle permanently in Poland. This especially applies to the Ukrainians who constitute a vast majority of immigrants in Poland and the Malopolska voivodeship.

1. Introduction

This report is a part of deliverable "D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries" of the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. The work on this topic was done within Work Package 6 in Task 6.2: "Thematic study 2 – Migration in Central and Eastern European Countries – destination & origin region in the future - analysis of immigration and emigration patterns and integration of immigrants in EU CEE countries".

The aim of this part of Task 6.2. was to conduct a survey of immigrants coming to selected CEE country focusing on determinants of migration, attitudes, perceptions, and behaviours of migrants as well as issues related to integration and assimilation. The results of the study provide additional information for building new migration scenarios for the region used in other parts of the project. The work contributes to FUME attempt to shed light on *local factors attracting migrant settlement* (Research Question RQ2). In particular, it is crucial to get a deeper understanding of the settlement behaviours in the EU CEE countries. This is due to the fact that in recent years, most of the EU Member States from Central and Eastern Europe have undergone transformation from 'migrant-exporting' economies into important destinations (Okólski, 2012; Bilan & Strielkowski, 2016). Albeit this transformation from a sending into a host country is not exceptional phenomenon in Europe - the same processes in the South European members of the EU such as Spain or Italy were observed (Bonifazi et al., 2009), the pace of this transformation is unprecedented. The striking example in this regard is Poland. Since 2015, it has turned into a major destination country for third-country nationals in the EU. Before 2015, less than 0.5 per cent of the population was foreign-born. Most recent estimates (2020) mention 2,2 million immigrants residing in Poland in February 2020 (5.8 per cent of the population) – among them 1,35 million Ukrainians and a few dozens of thousands of immigrants from other countries (i.e. Belarus, Russia, Germany, Moldova and India – to mention those with the largest communities in Poland - GUS 2020).

Consequently, we have decided to choose Poland as a perfect case study, which is somehow emblematic for entire CEE area. It is the largest economy of the region and it is – in contrary to Hungary or Czech Republic which have experience with former immigration waves, albeit on lower scale – experiencing the first important immigration wave from 1918, i.e. the rebirth of Poland as a nation state. The Polish case is also important, as Poland is economically connected to Germany, a major destination country for migrants in the EU. Moreover, in 2020 Germany has opened its labour market to some third country nationals, including Ukrainians who comprise most of immigrant population in Poland. Therefore, some experts expressed concern that Ukrainian immigrants would move from Poland to Germany. Some experts estimated this flow on the level on between 200 and 500 thousand persons. Albeit these threats did not materialize, mostly due to covid-19 pandemic and subsequent restrictions in international mobility, the concerns about possible re-emigration of Ukrainians from Poland remained in the public discourse (Bartman, 2021).

Our survey on immigrants and their settlements practices and plans was a challenging task, as immigration in Poland is a recent phenomenon. The country has been perceived as a traditional country of emigration. This also had implications for migration studies in Poland. Most of research projects until 2015 focused on post-accession migration movements from the Polish territory and on the Polish diaspora. Consequently, a few existing immigration studies focused mostly on qualitative analyses based on in-depth interviews, focus group interviews or analyses of written content, such as the social media (Brzozowska, 2018).

In the case of quantitative analyses in Poland, the biggest challenge was lack of register of foreigners/immigrants which would enable researchers to select a representative sample from this group of Polish society and conduct proper inferential statistical analysis. Consequently, the major approach in surveying immigrants so far was the Respondent-Driven Sampling (RDS), adopted by the Centre for Migration Research (CMR) at the University of Warsaw. RDS is a method used to survey the hidden populations, whose real number is difficult to obtain or even estimate – such as persons infected with HIV (Gile, 2011) or drug addicts (Wenz et al., 2016). Studies which apply RDS are based on a modified snowballing sampling, where the „seeds” are instructed to recruit a more heterogenous group of respondents based on age, gender, or education or other socio-economic characteristics. Another important modification towards the classical snowballing is the inclusion in RDS the system of double motivations – both “seeds” (recruiters) and the participants are paid for their participation (Górny and Jaźwińska, 2019). Without a sound access to population registers, RDS became the dominant methodological approach in surveying immigrants in Poland, as it enabled to generalize the results on the entire migrant population. Unfortunately, the RDS as every method is not perfect: one of the problematic issues is that the reliability of results greatly depends on the generality of the migration network, which in the case of recently arrived immigrants might be problematic (Griffiths et al., 2017).

Another method, even more problematic when it comes to its reliability is the application of a survey with occasional sampling, which in fact is also a variation of snowballing sampling. Such method was used in the pioneering study on socio-economic integration of immigrants in Małopolska region (Brzozowski and Pędziwiatr, 2014), or the analysis of the integration of Ukrainian students in Małopolska and Podkarpacie regions (Długosz, 2018). Without possibilities of further generalization, these studies were mostly explorative and aimed at testing some new tools for integration measurement, such as ethnosizer (Brzozowski and Pędziwiatr, 2015).

The traditional representative surveys on immigrant populations, which are widespread in the Western Europe, are still a novelty in Poland. Currently the only register of foreigners covering the entire territory of the country is the Pobył register system, administered by Office for Foreigners (Urząd do Spraw Cudzoziemców - UdSC) of the Polish government. The main problem of the system is dispersion of detailed information about foreigners legalizing their stay on the territory of Poland between the regional units of administration responsible for registering foreigners in Polish voivodeships. For example, the general register Pobył at the central level (UdSC) does not contain contact information to foreigners such as the phone numbers – in most cases such data is available in paper documentation, which is kept in regional offices for foreigner matters at each voivodeship office. In the FUME project, we therefore have turned for assistance to Małopolska voivodeship and the survey of immigrants was conducted in Małopolska region. This implies that

FUME survey of immigrants aims to be representative for Małopolska voivodeship. The selection of representative sample for entire Poland from Pobył register is extremely difficult and would require the active participation of 16 voivodeship's administrative offices for foreigners.

The Centre for Advanced Studies of Population and Religion (CASPAR) at Cracow University of Economics – a consortium partner of the FUME project responsible for carrying out the survey – formally signed an agreement on scientific cooperation with the Department for Foreigners' Affairs at Małopolska Voivodeship Office in 2021. This agreement regulates the access to Pobył register for scientific usage: nevertheless, the data received from Department is anonymized. Consequently, to construct the sample for survey purposes, the active participation of the employees of the Department was mandatory, as only the officers of the Department have the access to personal files and documents of foreigners, including phone numbers and addresses.

In June 2021, the public procurement process was started to choose the private company responsible for conduction fieldwork of the FUME survey. After receiving the offers from several institutions, CASPAR research center has chosen company DANAE Sp. z o.o., who has initiated the activities in August 2021. The description of methodology is provided in the next section. We have collected 599 questionnaires: 499 respondents were immigrants from third countries, and 100 were EU nationals.

Picture: Jean Carlo Emer/Unsplash.com

2. Methodology

The survey questionnaire has been prepared jointly by research team from CASPAR, Statistics Denmark, and the DANAE. It contains 40 questions, including such aspects as personal and family characteristics, migration experience, re-emigration declarations and preparedness and/or declarations of settlement in Poland, economic activity, socio-cultural integration, health condition etc. The questionnaire was prepared in 4 language versions: in Polish, English, Russian and Ukrainian. The pilot study was conducted on 18th of September 2021 in TAPI (Tablet Assisted Personal Interview) form at site of the Department for Foreigners' Affairs at Małopolska Voivodeship Office. 25 respondents participated in the pilot. After the pilot, small changes in the questionnaire were introduced to facilitate the survey and make the questionnaire more understandable for respondents. The final version of the questionnaire (in English) is available in the appendix of this report.

In the second step, the stratified sampling procedure was applied. From the Pobył register 4 groups - strata of respondents: 1) third country nationals from Europe residing in Kraków 2) third country nationals coming outside of Europe residing in Kraków 3) third country nationals from Europe residing outside of Kraków and 4) third country nationals coming outside of Europe residing outside Kraków. It is important to mention, that Kraków – the capital of Małopolskie voivodeship – attracts the vast majority of immigrant population in region (69.6 per cent, cf. Pędziwiatr et al., 2019). In the next step, in each stratum we used proportional allocation sampling based on such criteria as age, gender, education level and the legal status (permanent/temporary residence permit). In this way, an initial stratified group of 2000 persons was selected. These persons were contacted, in the fourth step, by phone by the officers of the Department for Foreigners' Affairs at Małopolska Voivodeship Office to reach expected sample size and composition that mimic distribution in each stratum. For example, in a final sample 4 persons with certain characteristics were needed, thus, we sampled 4 times of these value (16 persons) for the selected group (2000 persons). The officers phoned randomly chosen individuals from those 16 people to reach 4 approvals. When the objective was reached, they moved to the next subgroup. The officers verified correctness of the information in the Pobył register and asked the foreigners for the consent to participate in our research. The anonymized contact details of persons who agreed to take part in the study (i.e. phone numbers and e-mail addresses) was delivered to the FUME research team (714 immigrants). Finally, between 19th of October 2021 and 31st of December 2021, the company DANAE carried out a survey fieldwork using mostly CATI (Computer-Assisted Telephone Interview) and CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interview) methods. As we had only access to potential respondents who have agreed to participate in the survey, the response rate was very high and reached 69.9 per cent (499 respondents). Thus, we have a strong grounds to believe that a sample is representative for the population of immigrants in Małopolska voivodeship and in Kraków and the results of survey can be generalized on the total population.

When it comes to EU nationals, the Pobył register does not include important contact details to those persons (f.i. phone numbers, email addresses) due to a different registration form used in a residence legalization procedure for this group. Therefore, we could not select a sample from this data source as for third country nationals. Because of that, in December 2021, the FUME research team carried out a PAPI survey in the office of the Department for Foreigners' Affairs at Małopolska Voivodeship Office and obtained 100 complete questionnaires. Thus, our full sample consists of 599 respondents. However, when it comes to the EU

nationals, the sample was selected using a nonrandom convenience sampling and due to applied procedure the information of rejection of participation was not recorded and consequently information on response rate for this group is not available. Thus, the sample cannot be treated as representative for the population of immigrants with EU citizenship who live in Małopolska voivodeship. However, to reduce the bias on non-random selection weights created based on distribution of characteristics of total population of EU nationals were applied in the analysis.

3. Description of survey sample

We have received 599 valid responses in the FUME survey – 499 from foreign-born persons originated from Third countries and 100 from persons with EU citizenship. The structure of the sample is very young - over 1/3 of respondents are in age group 18-29, almost the same share in 30-39 group and only a third in 40+ age group. There is a dominance of males in the sample - females constitute around 41% of respondents. These results are very similar to the ones from registers of social insurance, where economically active population of immigrants in Malopolska voivodeship, where females comprised 38% of this group in 2020 (Pędziwiatr et al., 2020).

Picture: Alvaro Sanchez/Unsplash.com

Table 1. Descriptive statistics on respondents

Source: Own elaboration.

Age of respondents	%	Country of origin	%
18-29	33.90	Ukraine	71.30
30-39	32.99	UK	4.50
40+	33.11	Belarus	3.70
Gender	%	Other	20.50
Female	40.95	Civil status	%
Male	59.05	Single	33.23
Place of residence	%	Cohabitation	8
Kraków	71.60	Married	50.44
Małopolska non-KRK	28.40	Widowed	1.90
Region of origin	%	Divorced	5.37
Europe Non EU	77.63	Prefers not to say	1.06
Europe EU+	15.69	Children	%
Outside Europe	6.68	None	51.71
Legal status	%	One	24.06
Temporary residence	69.01	Two	18.43
Permanent residence	11.85	Three	4.95
EU residence	18.43	4+	0.85
Other	1.33	Children live in Poland	61
		Children in other country	39
Education	%		%
Primary	3.84	Bachelor	28.71
Secondary	34.56	Master	25.21
Postsecondary	5.67	PhD or equivalent	2

When it comes to the place of residence, most of the respondents live in Kraków (71.6%) which is also consisted with the general population of immigrants (69.5%, cf. Pędziwiatr et al., 2019). Kraków is the capital and the main economic center of Małopolska voivodeship, with booming B2B/outsourcing industry, well-developed tourism sector and an important academic city with several major public and private universities. All these factors attract immigrants to Kraków. Nevertheless, 28.4% of our respondents live outside of Kraków in other parts of Małopolska. Some of them commute to Kraków, some others work and live in other important cities such as Nowy Sącz and Tarnów, or in smaller cities and towns.

Our respondents originate mostly from European countries which are not members of the European Union (77.6%). As for the country of origin, the most common is Ukraine (71.3%) as this country is the most important sending country to Poland and also to Małopolska voivodeship.

As the population of immigrants in Małopolska is relatively young, there is a large fraction of persons who are single (33 %), while married comprise of around 50%. Most of immigrants do not have children (51.7%). Among immigrant parents 61% of their children live in Poland. Yet, 39% of children of immigrants live in other countries, in most cases – in Ukraine. This is because the massive migration of Ukrainians started only from 2015 and the process of family reunification has not started for many immigrants. Nevertheless, even such descriptive statistics indicate the temporary nature of immigration in Małopolska voivodeship and thus further investigation on the settlement intentions of respondents is needed.

Finally, the immigrant population in our sample is very well educated: 56 per cent has tertiary education, while 2 per cent received a PhD diploma. This data shows that immigrants constitute a valuable asset for employers and have high prospects for successful economic integration in Poland. Additionally, almost 25 per cent of respondents acquired at least some education in Poland, most of them higher education (20 per cent of total). This factor enhances their integration prospects even further.

Picture: Natali Hordiiuk/Unsplash.com

4. Socio-economic adaptation

Most of immigrants come to Poland because of economic reasons (see Figure 5, section 5). Moreover, the Polish economy is doing quite well, with unemployment level standing at just 5.6 per cent (Statistics Poland, 2021). Therefore, most of our respondents are full-time employed (75 per cent, see Figure 1). The share of unemployed persons is just slightly over the national average – 5.8 per cent. There is also a relatively large group of self-employed entrepreneurs (5.19 per cent), who compose 9 per cent of EU nationals. Finally, 5 per cent of respondents are currently studying, mostly at tertiary level. The differences between EU nationals (19.6 per cent in education) and immigrants with temporary residence permit (2.7 per cent in education) is due to different legal status of university students from non-EU countries. These are mostly Ukrainians and Byelorussians who enter Poland based on a student visa. Those persons do not legalize their stay via Voivodship administration and because of that they are not included in our sample.

Figure 1. Economic situation of an individual.

Source: Own elaboration.

Most of respondents evaluate their economic situation in optimistic way. They assess their economic condition as “rather well” (61 per cent, see Figure 2) and the disparity between EU nationals and immigrants with temporary residence is rather small in this regard. Additionally, almost one third of EU nationals (29.4 per cent) claims that they fare “very well” when it comes to their economic position.

Figure 2. Self-assessment of economic situation.

Source: Own elaboration.

Finally, one of surprising findings is very high scores on self-assessment of job satisfaction of surveyed individuals (Figure 3). Over a third of respondents exhibit high scores of job satisfaction (7 to 9 points: 34 per cent), while 40 per cent claim that they are fully satisfied with their work in Poland. Only around 11 per cent of immigrants are not satisfied with their current occupation.

Figure 3. Job satisfaction self-assessment (0-10).

Source: Own elaboration.

These results demonstrate that immigrants in Małopolska voivodeship are quite well integrated in economic aspect. Most of them get meaningful employment which provides them with stable source of income.

Picture: Marjan Blan/Unsplash.com

5. Declarations on settlement and migration intentions

The most important section of our questionnaire was devoted to the previous migration experiences and future migration declarations (see the appendix for full questionnaire). For most of immigrants (84 per cent) the current migration episode is the first one in their lifetime (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. No previous migration experience (3 months or more).
Source: Own elaboration.

In the case of EU citizens, the share of persons with previous migration experience is slightly higher (29 per cent) than in the case of persons with temporary residence permit (mostly non-EU country nationals – 9.7 per cent with former migration experience), which might suggest their potential higher propensity to remigrate in the future.

Figure 5. Reasons for coming to Poland (multiple answers allowed).
Source: Own elaboration.

When it comes to reasons for coming to Poland, the most important one is the economic motivation. Yet, there is a great disparity in this regard when it comes to legal status of the respondents. Two thirds of temporary residence holders migrated to Poland because of the poor economic situation at home (Figure 5). Most of them are Ukrainians and Byelorussians. In the case of EU nationals the economic push factor was less common (18 per cent), while the personal reasons proved to be important (30.9 per cent) – many EU nationals have their relatives or partners in Poland. Other important factor is education (22 per cent), while, surprisingly, political situation at home was seldomly reported (10.6 per cent) despite the problems with autocratic regime in Belarus and domestic war in Ukraine.

Figure 6. Assistance received when organizing migration (multiple answers allowed).
Source: Own elaboration.

The biggest share of respondents arrived in Poland without external support (47 per cent, see Figure 6). One out of five has been helped in making migration arrangements by a family already located in Poland, while 19 per cent were helped by their friends living in Poland. These results show that migration networks are still not well developed as most of our respondents did not rely on them while travelling to Poland. Yet, this situation might change if immigration from Ukraine continues, which is expected in 2022 due to difficult political and economic situation in that country (including possible military conflict with Russia).

The respondents were also asked about plans of respondents, including the declaration of settlement or further remigration from Poland. Surprisingly, a vast majority of our respondents declared that they want to settle permanently in Poland (75 per cent, see Figure 7). The share of those willing to stay permanently in the country is the highest among the biggest group of immigrants – Ukrainians (81 per cent), while for the EU nationals is the lowest (55 per cent). It is worth mentioning here that declarations of migration very often do not materialize in the future (Brzozowski and Coniglio, 2021), but very little is known about the future realizations in the case of the declarations of permanent settlements by immigrants. Nevertheless, our results indicate that the recently-arrived immigrants to Poland after 2015 are mostly here to stay, not to remigrate to Germany or back to their home country.

Figure 7. Declarations on the length of stay in Poland.

Source: Own elaboration.

This statement is additionally backed up by the answers to the question on future migration plans (Figure 8). Even higher percentage of immigrants declare no future migration plans (76 per cent) than the ones who wish to settle permanently in Poland (75 per cent). Actually, more persons have unspecified plans for the future (16 per cent) than the ones who can already indicate direction of future migration movement – home country (6.4 per cent of respondents) or another country (1.3 per cent).

Figure 8. Considers migrating in the future.

Source: Own elaboration.

Picture: Marta Zwierzchoniewska/Unsplash.com

6. Conclusions

The analysis of information from the FUME survey provide evidence on aspirations and behaviours of immigrants in Poland – one of the group of EU countries from CEE that recently attract large number of foreigners. Most of immigrants from the recent wave, after 2015, arrived in Poland due to economic reasons, not political ones. Consequently, immigrants in Poland are well-integrated in economic aspects. Most of them have full-time employment and assess their financial situation as satisfactory.

When it comes to settlement and remigration plans, to our surprise a number of persons who wish to stay permanently in Poland is very large. Actually, 75 per cent of respondents declared that they intend to stay permanently in Poland, while among Ukrainians, who account for ca. 70-75 per cent of all migrants, this share is even higher – 81per cent. Therefore, the recent immigration in Poland should not be perceived as a temporary phenomenon. Many newcomers would like to stay in Poland for a longer period, even permanently. This implies a need of a further development of integration policy – not only in economic aspect, but also in socio-cultural areas.

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Appendix

Hello, I am an interviewer for Danae, we are doing a study on your migration experience. The project is commissioned by the Centre of Advanced Population and Religious Studies at Cracow University of Economics. The research in which you are participating is a part of the FUME project implemented using Horizon2020 funds. The aim of the study is to determine the immigration potential in Poland. Our respondents remain anonymous, and the data obtained will be used solely for research purposes and will be analyzed collectively. Thank you in advance for taking part in the survey, if any question seems troublesome for you, you can refuse answering it.

S1. Questionnaire language

- Polish
- English
- Ukrainian
- Russian

BLOK 1. DANE OSOBOWE (METRYCZKA)

M1. Age

|_|_|

M2. Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Other

M3. Country of birth

M4. What is your legal status in Poland?

- Permanent residence permit
- Temporary residence permit
- Residence permit for a European Union citizen
- Visa
- Other, what?
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

M5. What is your marital status?

- Single
- Steady partner
- Marriage
- Widow(er)
- Divorce
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

M6. Partner's place of birth

- _____
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M7. In what country is your partner currently staying at?

- _____
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M8_1. How many children do you have?

- |_|_|
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M8_2. How many of are your biological children?

- |_|_|
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M8_3. Number of adopted children

|_|_|

M8_4. How old are your children? / How old is your child?

- First child |_|_|
- Second child |_|_|
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M8_5. Where are your children currently staying at? / Where is your child currently staying at?

- First child _____
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse
- Second child _____
- Difficult to say
 - Refuse

M9. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Primary education
- Lower secondary education
- Upper secondary education
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education
- Short-cycle tertiary education
- Bachelor's or equivalent level
- Master's or equivalent level
- Doctoral or equivalent level

M10. Years of education

|_|_|

- Difficult to say
- Refuse

M11. Education level obtained in Poland

- Primary / lower secondary education
- Upper secondary education
- Bachelor's
- Master's
- Doctoral
- None

M12. From which year and month, Poland has been your main place of residence?

Year |_|_|_|_|

Month |_|_|

- Difficult to say
- Refuse

BLOK 2. HISTORIA I PLANY MIGRACYJNE

A1. Is the current stay in Poland your first experience abroad (lasting at least 3 months)?

- Yes
- No
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

A2a. How many times did you leave for more than 3 months? Include also your current stay.

Number of migration courses

|_|_|

A2b. To which countries did you go?

First country of residence _____

Second country of residence _____

A3. Why did you come to Poland? More than one answer is possible.

- Because of poor economic situation at home
- Purpose of education or study
- Family or partner in Poland
- To start my own business
- Due to the difficult political situation in the country
- Other – what? _____

A4. Did anyone help you organize your arrival? More than one answer is possible.

- No, I arrived by myself
- Yes, family in Poland helped me
- Yes, friends in Poland helped me
- Yes, the intermediary organizing the arrival helped me
- I was seconded by my employer
- Other, what? _____

A5. How long do you plan to stay in Poland?

- Less than a year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- Permanently
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

A6. Do you consider migration to another country or to the homeland?

- Yes, to the homeland
- Yes, to another country SKRYPTER: Wyświetl rozwijaną listę krajów
- I don't consider migration
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

A7. When you are considering your next migration?

- Within 0-3 months
- Within 4-12 months
- Within 1-2 years
- Within 2-5 years
- In more than 5 years
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

A8. Have you taken any steps in this direction? It is possible to mark more than one answer.

- Yes, I'm planning a trip
- Yes, I'm looking for a job
- Yes, I'm looking for a apartment
- Yes, other
- No

A9. Does the covid-19 epidemic affect your decision about the length of your stay in Poland?

- Doesn't affect
- Affects
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B1. What is your current work situation? More than one answer is possible

- Full-time
- Odd, part-time
- Entrepreneur
- Job without a contract
- Looking for a job
- Education, studies
- Unemployed
- Parental leave
- Pension, retirement pension
- Other, what? _____
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B2. Have you changed the form of employment due to the covid-19 epidemic and the economic slowdown?

It is possible to mark more than one answer.

- Changed an employer
- The work is the same, but the employment dimension has decreased Straciłem(am) pracę
- Started up my own company
- Take up education (studies, courses)
- I am on a compulsory vacation
- I works without a contract
- Nothing has changed
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B3. What industry do you currently work in?

- Public sector
- Agriculture
- Construction
- Industry
- Transport
- Trade
- Tourism
- Gastronomy
- Education
- Services
- Services for business / B2B
- Other, what? _____
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B4. How would you rate your current financial situation?

- I am very badly off and in a difficult financial situation
- I am doing rather badly
- I do well, on average
- I am doing rather well
- I am doing very well
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B5. Do you use or have you used any of the following benefits? More than one answer is possible

- Family allowance and allowance supplements
- Childbirth grants
- 500+
- Allowance and/or care allowance
- 3+ Family card or Large Family Card
- Other, what? _____
- No
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B6. Please indicate your satisfaction with your job (business), where 0 means "no job satisfaction" and 10 means "high job satisfaction"

- 0 - no job satisfaction
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 - very high job satisfaction
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

B7. Please specify the degree of matching your qualifications to your job (business activity), where 0 means "not at all" and 10 means "fully matched"

- 0 - no match at all
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 - fully matched
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

BLOK 4. INTEGRACJA SPOŁECZNO-KULTUROWA

C1. Do you consider Poland as your home?

- Definitely no
- Probably no
- Probably yes
- Definitely yes
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C2. How do you assess your knowledge of Polish language?

- Don't know at all
- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very Good
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C3. Have you ever been learning Polish?

- I have never been
- Yes, I have started but i stopped
- Yes, I'm still learning

C4. How do you assess your knowledge of English language?

- Don't know at all
- Very poor
- Poor
- Average
- Good
- Very Good
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C5. How many of your friends were born abroad of Poland or have foreign parents?

- None
- About 25%
- About 50%
- About 75%
- All of them
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C6. Religion is an essential part of my life.

- Definitely no
- Rather no
- Rather yes
- Definitely yes
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C7. How often do you participate in devotions, religious meetings, and collective prayers?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Few Times a year
- Once a month
- Every week
- Every day
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C8. Which church or religious association do you belong to?

- The Catholic church
- The Armenian Catholic Church
- The Greek Catholic Church
- The Lutheran Church or other Protestant association
- The Orthodox Church
- Sunni Islam
- Shi'ite Islam
- Hinduism
- Buddhism
- Other, what? _____
- I don't belong to any religion
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C9. How would you describe your attitude towards faith?

- Atheist
- Agnostic
- Other, what? _____
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C10. What is, in your opinion, the attitude of Polish society towards people who came to Poland from your country of origin?

- Definitely unfriendly
- Rather unfriendly
- Neutral
- Rather friendly
- Rather unfriendly
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C11. Have you ever experienced discrimination:

	1 Never	2 Rarely	3 Quite often	4 Very often	97 Not applicable	98 Difficult to say	99 Refuse
At work	1	2	3	4	97	98	99
During looking for an apartment	1	2	3	4	97	98	99
At school or University	1	2	3	4	97	98	99
In another dimension of social life - what?	1	2	3	4	97	98	99

C12. Where do you currently live?

- I rent a house/flat independently
- I rent a room at a flat/house
- I live with relatives, friends or my employer
- I live at my own flat/house
- Other, what? _____
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C13. Do other immigrants live in your neighbourhood? It is possible to mark more than one answer.

- Yes, other people from my national group live in the area
- Yes, there are foreigners from a different national group than mine
- I don't care, I'm not interested SKRYPTER: wyklucz inne odpowiedzi
- No, only Polish people live in the area SKRYPTER: wyklucz inne odpowiedzi
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C17. I decided to live in the current place because of ... It is possible to mark more than one answer.

- Proximity to work
- Comfort of living
- Availability of public infrastructure (schools, kindergartens, hospitals, offices)
- Nice and safe environment
- The proximity of other people from the country where I was born
- Low cost of living in this place
- Proximity to the temple, the prayer rooms of my religious community or the headquarters of my national group organization
- I hadn't any influence on my place of residence.
- Another reason what? _____
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C15. How do you rate your housing conditions?

- Very poor
- Poor
- On average
- Good
- Very good
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C16. Has the covid-19 epidemic affected your housing conditions?

- No
- Yes – they worsened
- Yes – they got better
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C17. How do you rate your entire life so far on a scale of 0-10, where 10 is the maximum?

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C18. Have you been feeling happy recently? Please rate on a scale of 0-10

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C19. In the last two weeks, have you felt:

	All the time	Most of time	A little more than half of time	A little less than half of time	Minority of the time	Not at all	Difficult to say	Refuse
Worsening of mood or sadness	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
loss of interest in daily activities	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
feeling tired and lacking energy to perform	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
weakening of concentration and attention, for example, reading newspapers or watching TV	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
low self confidence	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
guilt or unclean conscience	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
feeling dim or slowed down	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
high level of anxiety	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
feeling lack of sense in life	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
trouble sleeping at night	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
worsening of appetite	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99
excessive appetite	6	5	4	3	2	1	98	99

C20_1. Did you smoke cigarettes in the month preceding your arrival in Poland?

- Yes
- No
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C20_2. About how many cigarettes a day did you smoke on average then?

|||

- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C21_1. Did you smoke cigarettes in the previous month, i.e. in September 2021?

- Yes
- No
- Difficult to say
- Refuse

C21_2. How many cigarettes per day did you smoke on average in the previous month, i.e. in September 2021?

|_|_|

- Difficult to say
- Refuse

